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ABSTRACTS

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Computational drug repurposing approach to obtain potential anti-HEV molecules

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Abstract: Hepatitis E virus (HEV), responsible for acute viral hepatitis, is endemic in Central Asia, Africa and Central America with severity especially high in pregnant women. Side effects of off-label therapies and lack of effective antivirals warrant exploring the existing drugs for anti-HEV activity through drug repurposing. Transcriptome analysis of infected cells to that of control cells allows identifying changes in the gene expression pattern after acquiring disease to get potential drug candidates which would reverse the effect. The study compared these patterns and identified a few potential anti-HEV molecules using a computational drug repurposing approach.

Gene mapping of available wet-lab RNA-seq data resulted in successful mapping of about 49 to 89 % of genes on the reference genome. 203 up-regulated and 311 downregulated genes were obtained. Total 85 drugs (which reverse the altered DEG pattern) were obtained from cMAP using top 150 up and downregulated genes. 15 drugs were finalised by eliminating drugs having low scores, and those without any known animal and cell line toxicity values. Two DEGs, LGALS9 and NRC2 were obtained with associated potential drug candidates and GO (pathway) terms. LGALS9 coding for galectin 1 and galectin 9 protein products affect biological pathways crucial for viral entry in host cell (GO:0046598) and also responsible for regulation of CD4-positive, CD25-positive, alpha-beta regulatory T cell differentiation involved in immune response (GO:0032832). These dictated the identification of the following molecules of high anti-HEV potential: Mercaptoethanol; Thiodigalactoside; 1,4-Dithiothreitol; Arteminol; (R)-1-Para-Nitro-Phenyl-2-Azido-ethanol.

Keywords: Hepatitis E virus, transcriptome, gene mapping, cMAP.

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